

A Review on Organization Culture and Employee Performance

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Abstract

This study is focusing on how the employee performance is being affected by the organizational culture and what is the relationship between two. After going through several previous studies and research on employee performance and organizational culture it's verified that there is a relation between the organizational culture and employee performance. The study aims to identify the factors of organization culture that have an impact over the performance of employees and how it increases or decreases the performance. How the culture of an organization affects people, their surroundings, process, and systems is assessed through different literature reviews on the employee performance and organization culture. Relationship between the employees is based on the norms and values of an organization according to previous surveys. To increase the performance of employees, employee development through different strategies is highly crucial and should be the goal of an organization to accomplish the desired outcome.

Keywords: Employee Performance, Strategies, Organizational Culture

Introduction

An organization's way of life is its set of standards, values, and principles that serve as a guide for employees to know what is expected of them and what is not. These beliefs significantly affect both individual behaviour and the effectiveness of the organisation as a whole. In reality, the phrase "organisational style of life" became popularised in the 1980s by Peters and Waterman's best-selling book in Search of Excellence, in which they argued that company success is attributable to a decisive, customer-oriented, empowering, and community-focused way of life (Ivancevich, Matteson, & Konopaske, 1990).

The evolution of organised life since then has been the subject of many experiments documented in books, journals, and other forms of written research. A lot of the time, people don't even notice culture exists, much as fish don't see the water. Comparing one's company culture to that of competitors raises awareness of the company's way of life because of the impact it has on all aspects of an employee's behaviour, thought, and action (Sadker, & Zittleman, 2007).

Deal & Kennedy (1983) argued that an agency has to play an outsized function with inside the increase of its employees as manner returned-workplace features and be intently tied to its middle way of life as some distance returned as 1982 to decorate their productiveness The organizing feature entails growing and enforcing organizational layout selections.

The way of life of the agency is intently related to organizational layout. For instance, a way of life that empowers personnel to make selections ought to show extraordinarily immune to a centralized organizational layout, hampering the manager's capacity to enact this type of layout (Rosenbloom, Kravchuk, & Clerkin, 2009).

Organizational way of life is an essential detail that unites diverse company cultures (Morris, 1998). Managers can also additionally set up a powerful organizational way of life to combine the organizational way of life and

to enhance overall performance (Kaplan, Kaplan, Norton, & Norton, 2004). Successful cultural integration inside is an essential detail to keeping a success conversation and enhancing overall performance (Idris, Wahab, & Jaapar, 2015). Establishing a powerful organizational way of life is vital to enhance overall performance and productiveness (Pathiranage, Jayatilake, & Abeysekera, 2020).

Organizational development has certain factors that increase sustainability based on performance. Improving performance increases employee commitment because norms, values, and goals help improve an organization's culture. The organizational system was based on the effective creation of a culture that supported a strong learning environment. Build a strong organizational culture to increase employee productivity (Govindarajulu, & Daily, 2004).

Employee performance will be considered as the backbone of the organization as it effectively leads to the growth of the organization. Employee loyalty based on cultural knowledge and awareness improves organizational behavior (Brooks, Wiley & Hause, 2006). Organizational culture was first defined by Quarterly Administration Science (Pettigrew, 1979). Employee values and standards are based on identifying leadership that improves employee performance and effectiveness. Quality consciousness improves organizational and employee growth.

The effect of company culture on efficiency and effectiveness has been the subject of a great deal of study. The economic success of a company, according to some academics, may be correlated with its cultural norms (Hofstede, 1980; Ouchi, 1981; Hofstede & Bond, 1988; Kotter & Heskett, 1992; Magee, 2002). However, there is some causal uncertainty between the cultural traits of different organisations and the levels of organisational excellence they achieve (Barney, 1991; Peters & Waterman, 1982). Our workers' needs and expectations, like the rest of the world, are always evolving. Organizational culture coordinates throughout time to respond to such shifting needs and ensure all workers feel appreciated and valued. Therefore, a positive work environment is considered as a motivating tool that helps workers get along and works to boost output (Ritchie, 2000). (Ritchie, 2000). Several aspects of corporate culture are the subject of ongoing studies. For instance, organisational psychology (Schein, 1985) zeroes on on how culture influences employee psychology and performance, while the kind of organisational culture (Tharp, 2009) stresses the degree of culture across the company. I am. These two aspects of an organization's culture demonstrate the connection between culture and employee output (Sagawa & Segal, 2000; Deem, 2003). Every organization is made up of three elements: people, goals, and systems. People work in systems to achieve the goals of an organization or people. Organizational culture includes organizational goals, values, and interactions with the external environment (Schein, 1983).

An organization's culture consists of its values, conventions, traditions, and written and unwritten regulations. Contrary to popular belief, it is very difficult to alter the culture of any given business. A company's culture may be evaluated using a number of different frameworks and typologies of organisational culture. This research will focus on the three most prevalent types of organisational culture: bureaucratic, creative, and sustaining (Abid Alvi, Hanif, Adil, Ahmed, & Vveinhardt, 2014).

Emotional commitment concerns the work of the employee and the employee's connection and loyalty to the boss and boss, and emotional organizational commitment is the employee's constant commitment to his or her organization in all of conditions. Think assertively and answer. Continuing commitment means that an employee wants to stay in the current organization because of possible statutory or leaving costs, or because the employee could not find a substitute option. Normative commitment refers to employee awareness of the organization, employee loyalty, and commitment to work and the organization (Allen, & Meyer, 1990).

Work satisfaction is employee satisfaction with the work. Work satisfaction is an emotional feeling about wages, pensions, working conditions, overall work and work satisfaction with time. Work satisfaction is how employees feel about their work and the various factors that affect it. It's employee satisfaction with their work. Negative attitudes towards your work can be dissatisfaction with your work. Employee satisfaction refers to the enjoyment of the work environment. Supervisors, organizational benefits, workloads, promotions (Judge, Zhang, & Glerum, 2020; Nagar, 2012).

Organizational Culture

The study and teaching of organisational culture is one of the most common fields of study and instruction in the fields of both organisational structure theory and managerial practise. Reasonable justifications include: Everything that happens in an organisation, from day to day to long-term planning, is influenced by cultural norms (Kolb, & Kolb, 2009).

The ways in which people in an organisation think, feel, value, and behave are guided by ideas, meanings, and beliefs of a cultural (socially shared) character, even in settings where cultural concerns are not given much attention. It doesn't matter whether managers dismiss culture as unimportant because they find it too nebulous a concept or because they can't pin it down to a single source. format for how the corporate world should be comprehended. Companies that engage in extensive "numbers management" may create and perpetuate a culture that glorifies KPIs and other metrics of quantitative success and their management. Most contemporary businesses place a premium on corporate culture, and most of those businesses believe it to be very important (Alvesson, 2015). However, even when upper-level managers have a solid grasp of the significance of culture, they frequently lack a deeper comprehension of how people and organisations function in terms of culture. Understanding and 'using' culture in a considered manner is challenging because of its complexity and significance (Al-Alawi, Al-Marzooqi, & Mohammed, 2007).

Cultures vary greatly from one another. A social group is defined as a subset of an organisation with its own shared customs, values, and objectives that emerge through its interaction with its specific environment (Schein, 1995). Awareness of how one's actions shape the company's culture is a precondition for loyalty on the part of employees (Lok, Westwood, & Crawford, 2005). The worker's values, beliefs, and worldview should firmly anchor them in culture (Deal, & Kennedy, 1983).

Strong organisational cultures have a beneficial influence on worker productivity. This was shown by (Martins & Terblanche, 2003). The worker should place a high value on the foundations. Organizational success is contingent on employees benefiting from the rules, procedures, and targets established by higher-ups. Philosophy, sentiments, assumptions, hopes, thoughts, conventions, and values are all components of a well-defined culture. U.S. writers of books on management in business used it as a jumping off point for their own work. In 1979, an editorial published in the journal *Body Science* introduced the notion of organisational culture to the academic community. Despite its extensive interest, the concept of "structure culture" has not been universally agreed upon in the organisation theory literature. This general lack of consensus on the concept's meaning and breadth may be traced back to the following issues.

- Treating culture as a unitary concept reduces its worth as an analytic tool.
- Culture cannot be equated to power, politics, or climate.
- There has not been a consensus on whether organizational culture will be simply changed (Van Wart, 2014).

A study by Wallach (1983) acknowledges the dominant options of structure culture, and it conjointly explains and simplifies the findings of (Hofstede, 1980.regarding the culture. Culture and high money performance are considerably and powerfully connected to every alternative (McKey, & Waterman,1982).

An further research by Kotter and Heskett (1992) found that people's performances may vary depending on how much time they spend engaging in culturally significant activities, which in turn duplicate the acquired mind course configuration. A company's societal and economic values are inextricably linked to its structure, culture, and operational effectiveness.

Employee Performance

Employee performance plays a crucial in the development of an organization. Any firm is totally dependent on the how the employees of that firm or organization are going to perform which leads to either failure or the success of an organization. Because the performance of employee decides that how effective an organization is. Employees play the role of a pillar for the organization, they work for. To make employee performance productive as well as effective employee development is highly crucial because of individual or employee pave ways for the organization to accomplish their defined goals and escalate employee performance as well (Elena , 2000). Hence, the effective relation between the development and performance of employee is proportional to

the success of the organization. Because the employee development will lead to job satisfaction which is the key element in the growth of organization (Champathes, 2006). Employee development activities designed by the firm proves that how considerate the firm or the organization is about their employees and how much they are spending on their employees for development which will eventually help them to grow effectively, put effort, fully committed to their work and pave ways for their organization (Elena, 2000).

Due to the growing competitive nature between firms with one and other in order to accomplish the goal of being a successful firm, the employee performance has been affected due to different factors. Firstly, the factors which affect employee performance can be put under the category of inside environment. It includes the way they have been trained to work, co-operation from the management to the employees and the overall climate of the firm. Secondly the other factors could be placed under the category of job and employee factors. Job factors include following aspects. The authority employees have to make a decision, how they have been communicated (communication factor) and the environment provided by the organization (Diamantidis & Chatzoglou, 2019).

Employee performance can be affected due to multiple reasons. It could be due to the lack of motivation in the organization, the effect of outside environment, lack of consideration in the structure of the company, work burden, no satisfaction of the job they are doing (Brayfield, & Crockett, 1955).

Motivation of employees, discipline to escalate the employee performance and leadership style also have an influence on the performance of the employees. The study conducted on the factors affecting employee performance carried out the results that there is a positive impact of how the employees are motivated through different activities, how is the leadership style on the employees and the discipline and discipline should be the center of attention (Pawirosumarto, Sarjana, & Muchtar, 2017).

The concept of the employee engagement has been gaining the attention which this concept should have given before, for the last few years because it has a significant impact over the performance of employees. It plays a crucial role in enhancing the employee performance. Many factors are linked to the employee engagement which impacts performance and the well-being of employees (which includes both the physical and mental well-being) is one of them. Further factors of effective communication (communication barriers should be lowered), balance between work (a healthy balance) and life and mainly the leadership style which motivates employees to give their best. Hence they need to be focused in order to meet the desirable results by the organizations (Alban-Metcalf and Alimo-Metcalf, 2008).

Employee performance is basically a tool which helps to deal with employees in a manner to have a positive impact over their thoughts and behavior to meet the need of effective performance. To enhance or increase the performance of employees, employee participation should be focused. The goals should be clearly defined to the employees of the working organization which they are expected to fulfill. In order to manage the performance of employees the tools which are required are individual contacting every employee, training of the employees, their feedback of how satisfied they are and what is bothering them (on regular basis), manager's engagement with employees and their counseling of how to tackle a problem or difficult situation. This will pave way for the employees to work efficiently (McConnell, 2004).

Leadership style is one the significant factor which has an impact on the employee performance. It is defined as the way of providing guidance and directions to the employees by the executive and motivating them to provide their best by influencing their behavior. It is the ability to guide the employees working under him to work with confidence, provide them the vision of how to improve their performance and to be more productive to accomplish the set goals or standard of the organization. It is a binding force which binds the employees of an organization to work co-operatively, promote peer relation and increase the capability of their employees (Fisher, 1995)

According to a study conducted on the decrease level of employee performance, resulted that lack of motivation is another leading factor in reducing the employee performance and not achieving the desired outcome. It shows that motivational factors have a significant impact over the performance of employees (Altrasi & College, 2014).

Teamwork is also one of the factors that has a positive effect over the performance of employees. By working in groups co-operatively, employees can achieve the target. Teamwork among employees sets the standard for their organization (Alie, Beam, & Carey, 1998). Currently the business field is focusing on assigning projects to the employees which they are supposed to complete in groups with their co-workers and providing them with the opportunity to enhance their knowledge as well as their working skills (Hartenian, 2003). A study indicates that working in a group is more beneficial for the organization and the employee are more productive while working in groups as compared to working individually (Jones et al., 2007).

According to Cohen and Bailey (1999) working in groups provides the opportunity to the employees to be dependent on one another for the completion of task, as well as equally responsible for whatever the outcome of the assigned task will be. Teamwork reduces the risk of conflicts between employees, develops their working skills, increases the co-operation with feedback (Jones et al., 2007). Teamwork is a key element even for the non-profit organizations (Pfaff & Huddleston, 2003).

Development of a system and design such activities which promote teamwork should be center of all organizations for employee's well-being and increasing productivity. This development will eventually lead to the improvement of employees (Washer, 2006). Teamwork motivates the employees of an organization to develop good relationship with peers, polish their skills, enhance their proficiency, provide them with the opportunity to come up with more productive ideas, escalate employee performance, provide them the confidence, increase employee participation in decision making which eventually helps the firm or the organization to flourish more and more. Teamwork is quite profitable for the organizations as well. Hence, it shows that there is a vital relation between teamwork and performance of employees.

Conclusion

Kandula (2006) suggests that a strong structural culture may be the key to high-quality performance. More than that, it is said that even two businesses operating in the same industry and geographical region would not get the same outcomes using the same approach. In contrast to how a weak, negative culture may demotivate an amazing individual to underperform and find themselves unmatched, a strong, positive culture can turn a middling individual into an average entertainer and have them perform excellently (Kotter, 2008). Improvements in job performance have a significant effect on the strength of an organization's culture since they boost productivity. Workforce management is affected by culturally-based norms and values in the organization. In a well-run business, a strong company culture facilitates efficient human resource management. Employee productivity rises as a direct result of a company's net profit. When members of the same cultural group follow the same plan to maximise their resources, everyone benefits. In some contexts, an organization's culture may actually serve to enhance and even provide a competitive edge. Improvements in the organization's performance in terms of sustainability may be attributed in part to the level of employee involvement and the quality of teamwork present within it. The organization's longevity and performance are affected by the culture's kind and strength.

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